

Additional file 7: Questionnaire before ultrasound-guided lymph node biopsy (in English)

Question 1.

Please state your sex:

Male	<input type="checkbox"/>
Female	<input type="checkbox"/>

Question 2.

Please state your age:

..... years

The following questions concern your past experiences with biopsies or other medical procedures.

Question 3.

- a. Have you ever undergone inguinal lymph node biopsy sampling under local anesthetic?

No	<input type="checkbox"/>	If you answered 'no', please continue to question 4
Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	

- b. If you answered 'yes' to question 3a: How many times have you undergone an inguinal lymph node biopsy under local anesthetic?

..... times

- c. When was the last time that you have undergone an inguinal lymph node biopsy under local anesthetic?

...../..... (month/year)

Question 4.

a. Have you ever undergone a procedure under local anesthetic?

No	<input type="checkbox"/>	If you answered 'no', please continue to question 5
Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	

b. If you answered 'yes' to question 4a: How many times have you undergone a procedure under local anesthetic?

..... times

c. If you answered 'yes' to question 4a: when was the last time that you have undergone a procedure under local anesthetic?

...../..... (month/year)

Question 5.

What are your reasons for participating in this study? Please check the appropriate box(es). You can select multiple boxes.

I have a family member or friend with rheumatoid arthritis (RA), so I know how RA can affect someone's life and want to help.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I would like to help decrease RA burden for future patients.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I believe it is important to partake, if possible, in research projects to advance medicine in general.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I heard about it from my general practitioner / rheumatologist and wanted to help	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other, namely.....	<input type="checkbox"/>

Question 6.

Please indicate with a vertical mark on the lines below, how well prepared you feel for the lymph node biopsy procedure with respect to:

- a. understanding of the aim of the procedure and the background information

0 mm *100 mm*

I do not understand

I completely understand

- b. what to expect during the procedure

0 mm *100 mm*

I do not understand

I completely understand

- c. after-care

0 mm *100 mm*

I do not understand

I completely understand

- d. possible complications

0 mm *100 mm*

I do not understand

I completely understand

Question 7.

Please indicate with a vertical mark on the lines below, how anxious you are about undergoing the procedure:

0 mm *100 mm*

I am not anxious

I am very anxious

Question 8.

Please indicate with a vertical mark on the lines below, how much you dread to undergo the procedure:

0 mm *100 mm*

I do not dread the procedure

I dread the procedure
very much

